

PV Power Conditioning System with LLC Resonant Converter in DCM

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Abstract— This paper presents a DC-DC power conditioning system for photovoltaic (PV) panels. A series loaded resonant converter with galvanic isolation, also known as an LLC resonant converter is used to interface PV arrays to the batteries within an energy management system. The LLC converter is operated in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) in order to minimize the switching losses, even with the wide input voltage range. This mode of operation also makes LLC converters easy to parallel, which is desirable when multiple micro-converters are used instead of a centralized inverter. A perturb and observe maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm is implemented with just a voltage sensor. Its performance is compared to that of an MPPT algorithm using both voltage and current feedback. In this paper the PV power conditioning system is designed and implemented in the laboratory. Experimental measurements demonstrate the power conditioning system functionality.

I. INTRODUCTION

PV panels are very popular renewable energy sources and they are often interfaced directly to the AC grid. However the intermittent nature of solar energy has recently stimulated more integration with energy storage systems [1],[2]. In California utilities are required to have 200MW of energy storage by the end of 2014 as part of the implementation of the state's ambitious renewable energy portfolio [3]. As solar energy is not always used to interface directly an AC bus or the grid, some interest has risen towards DC interface of PV panels. PV panels can be used to charge batteries or to power DC distribution networks, which are presently being investigated for many applications from data centers to residential to DC microgrids. The focus of this paper is a PV power conditioning system feeding batteries or a DC bus. This type of system is used to harvest and store solar energy for later usage or to power DC loads. An example is PV arrays installed on a carport or garage roof and the energy harvested is used to charge electric vehicle (EV) batteries. Another application is residential PV systems with 380V DC distribution, which is becoming increasingly popular. In this paper a resonant DC-DC converter is presented which features:

- Galvanic isolation
- Current source behavior for easy paralleling
- Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) with a single sensor
- Constant efficiency

The above characteristics make this converter attractive to interface individual PV panels as opposed to centralized converters harvesting power from large PV arrays. The recent trend to replace centralized converters with small converters (sometimes called micro-converters [11]) that interface single PV panels is based on the need to reduce the negative effects of shading and manufacturing differences between panels. MPPT algorithms are more effective when applied to individual PV panels rather than a large array. The drawback of micro-converters compared to large centralized converters is obviously cost due to the increased quantity of electronic components. However as the cost of semiconductors continues to decrease and micro-converters are shown to increase the overall efficiency of the PV system [4], centralized converters will soon become history.

Resonant converters to interface PV panels to batteries or a DC bus have been recently investigated [5][6][7], although not all of the topologies reported feature galvanic isolation. Galvanic isolation may not be a requirement when the PV system does not interface directly to the utility grid, however it is always preferred to improve safety when a fault occurs and to reduce ground leakage currents. The topology analyzed in this paper is a full bridge series loaded resonant converter with galvanic isolation and voltage doubler as shown in Figure 1. This resonant converter with the high frequency transformer is also known as an LLC converter [8] and it has been reported in literature as working in different modes of operation. In [8] through [12] LLC converters similar to the one presented here are analyzed, but in all cases the mode of operation is continuous conduction mode (CCM), which has the disadvantage of variable efficiency with the PV output voltage. The topology depicted in Figure 1 operated in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) has not

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been previously presented for PV-to-DC interface application. In this paper it is shown that DCM results in minimization of the switching losses. Furthermore as the LLC converter behaves like a current source, it is a good topology for paralleling multiple PV modules with MPPT capability.

Figure 1. Schematic of the DC-DC LLC resonant converter with voltage doubler.

In the following sections of this paper the LLC converter is analyzed in DCM of operation, then the converter control system is presented together with the digitally implemented MPPT algorithm. Finally the hardware implementation of the entire PV power conditioning system is presented together with experimental measurements and conclusions.

II. ANALYSIS OF THE LLC CONVERTER IN DCM

The PV power conditioning system presented in this paper includes the DC-DC LLC converter shown in Figure 1. Since the output voltage of the solar panel is relatively low, there is a pressing need to boost the output voltage. The output of the converter features a voltage doubler in order to reduce the turns ratio of the transformer, which achieves galvanic isolation and voltage level shifting. The converter is operated in DCM, by limiting the minimum switching period, T_{sw} which is related to the resonant frequency, ω_0 :

$$T_{sw} \geq \frac{4\pi}{\omega_0} \quad (1)$$

The switching period T_{sw} comprises two resonant cycles as shown in Figure 2 which depicts one entire switching period of 14 μ s.

The analytical expression for the resonant current, $i_r(t)$ is given by (2) for the time interval $0 < t < t_1$ and by (3) for the time interval $t_1 < t < t_2$ shown in Figure 2 [12].

$$i_r(t) = \frac{V_s - Vr_0 - V_o}{\omega_0 L_r} \sin \omega_0 t \quad (2)$$

$$i_r(t) = \frac{V_s - Vr_{t1} + V_o}{\omega_0 L_r} \sin \omega_0 (t - t_1) \quad (3)$$

where V_s and V_o are the input DC voltage and reflected output DC voltage amplitudes respectively, L_r is the resonant inductance, Vr_0 is the capacitor voltage initial condition and Vr_{t1} is the capacitor voltage initial condition at $t = t_1$. The current returns to zero at $t = t_1 = \frac{\pi}{\omega_0}$ and again at

$t = t_2 = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0}$. The above equations are derived by solving the differential equation for the resonant tank circuit with the following assumptions:

- The voltage drops of the diode and solid state switch are neglected
- The transformer is ideal
- The output voltage V_o reflected to the primary is constant

Figure 2. Waveforms from analytical equations for DCM.

The analytical expression for the average output current of the LLC converter in DCM is obtained by integrating the absolute value of $i_r(t)$, as derived in (2) and (3), over the entire switching period [12]:

$$I_{out_avg} = \frac{1}{T_{sw}} \int |i_r(t)| dt = \frac{2}{T_{sw}} \int_0^{t_1} \frac{V_s + V_o}{\omega_0 L_r} \sin \omega_0 t dt - \frac{2}{T_{sw}} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{-V_s + V_o}{\omega_0 L_r} \sin \omega_0 t dt = \frac{8V_s}{\omega_0^2 L_r T_{sw}} = \frac{8V_s f_{sw}}{\omega_0^2 L_r} \quad (4)$$

The advantage of operating in DCM is that the power flow can be controlled by changing the switching frequency without affecting the switching losses. This is because the switches are turned on when only a small amount of current is flowing in the transformer and the switches are turned off under zero voltage conditions. Furthermore, (4) shows that the average output current, I_{out_avg} , is proportional to the switching frequency $f_{sw} = \frac{1}{T_{sw}}$, which makes the LLC

converter behave like a controllable current source. The average input current is derived in (5) using the power balancing equation, $P_{in}=P_{out}$ where $P_{in} = V_s I_{in_avg}$ and $P_{out} = V_o I_{out_avg}$.

$$I_{in_avg} = \frac{V_o I_{out_avg}}{V_s} = \frac{8V_o f_{sw}}{\omega_o^2 L_r} \quad (5)$$

Figure 3 shows experimental data plot of the average input current I_{in_avg} versus switching frequency f_{sw} for the LLC in DCM when the output voltage was 64 volts. The discrete data points were obtained experimentally by setting a fixed switching frequency and recording the resulting current. The line is a linear least squares approximation of the observed data. The linearization is used to establish the gain and offset used in the MPPT algorithm, described in the following section, to schedule the switching frequency based on the commanded current.

Figure 3. LLC converter switching frequency vs. input current measured data.

Another advantage of operating the converter of Figure 1 in DCM is that the diodes of the output rectifier operate under zero current switching condition (ZCS), because each diode turns off before the other turns on.

III. CONVERTER CONTROL AND MPPT ALGORITHM

The power converter presented in this paper is digitally controlled by a field programmable gate array (FPGA). An MPPT algorithm is embedded in the controller in order to optimize the power output of the PV module by varying the switching frequency of the LLC converter.

MPPT is part of every PV power conditioning system. MPPT algorithms automatically find the PV voltage and current at which the PV panel must operate to obtain maximum power at its output. Many MPPT algorithms have been studied over the last decades [14]. The perturb and observe (P&O) method of MPPT was chosen to be programmed in the LLC converter based on its simplicity and ease of implementation. The P&O algorithm determines the maximum power point by incrementing the PV array

output current and comparing the resultant power to the previously sampled power. If the power is increasing, the current will continue to be incremented. If the difference between the recent and previously sampled power is less than zero, the current is decremented. The P&O method of MPPT will then hunt around the maximum power point of the PV array.

The flow diagram of the P&O MPPT algorithm implemented in the LLC controller is shown in Figure 4. The P&O algorithm requires two inputs, the PV array output current I_d and voltage V_{cap} , to find the operating point that yields maximum power output of the PV array. The P&O algorithm calculates the power of the PV array by multiplying the current and voltage. The current and voltage values pass through a software based first-order low pass filter set at 30 Hz to eliminate any high frequency signal noise. An error signal is then developed by comparing the new output power to the previously sampled output power. Based on the polarity of the error signal, the MPPT algorithm will either incrementally increase or decrease the switching frequency. For example, if the new power value is larger than the previous, the P&O algorithm will continue to incrementally increase the load current until the power error changes polarity. This is accomplished in the control logic through the use of a comparator block that generates a Boolean output. The Boolean output drives a multiplexer that will either add or subtract the ΔI value coded in software. This will load the PV array to operating around its maximum power point based on the environmental conditions.

Figure 4. Block diagram of the P&O MPPT implementation.

A negative bias was observed when simulating the MPPT algorithm that is attributed to using low-pass filters on the output of each sensor. When comparing the new and previous power measurements, the resultant error signal is frequently equal to zero. This error signal is then compared

to zero and the Boolean output is used to determine whether the desired current is incremented or decremented ($\pm\Delta I$). Because the comparator checks if the error signal is greater than zero and the error signal is frequently equal to zero, a negative bias was induced causing the algorithm to drive the PV array output low. This negative bias was corrected by adding a comparator that checks if the error is equal to zero. When the Boolean output of this comparator is true, the current perturbation will toggle between incrementing and decrementing the desired current as each zero occurrence arises. When the Boolean output is false, the perturbation is based on the sign of the error signal. Lastly the error is integrated to define the desired load current.

The linear relationship in (5) between the average input current of the LLC converter in DCM and the switching frequency gives the opportunity to eliminate the PV current sensor when implementing the P&O MPPT algorithm. In this paper the switching frequency is used to create an observer of the PV current. The switching frequency is linearly proportional to the LLC average input current, I_{in_avg} in (5), which is an algebraic sum of both the PV array average output current and the average capacitor current, which is zero. If the controller tries to change I_{in_avg} quickly then the capacitor between the PV and the LLC converters will start to affect the dynamic behavior of the P&O algorithm. Thus the sampling rate for computing the power changes is kept low at 200Hz so that the assumption can be made that the average capacitor current is always zero. This means the 'delay' in Figure 4 is 5 ms.

Eliminating the PV current sensor reduces the overall cost and complexity of the power conditioner hardware as well as reducing the noise induced in the system. By scheduling the switching frequency, the algorithm estimates the PV current and determines an estimate of the PV array output power. In the following section the performance of the MPPT algorithm with and without the PV current sensor is demonstrated experimentally.

IV. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION AND MEASUREMENTS

An LLC converter as shown in Figure 1 was designed and implemented on a small custom printed circuit board (PCB) as shown in the photograph of Figure 5.

Figure 5. LLC converter set up on a custom PCB.

First, the functionality of a single LLC converter was demonstrated experimentally. Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the waveforms of one LLC converter operating in DCM at two different switching frequencies: 46.5 kHz and 94.3 kHz

respectively. The gate voltage is displayed for one pair of MOSFETs while the resonant voltage and current pulses are shown for both pairs of MOSFETs. At the higher switching frequency, the resonant pulses occur more frequently and result in a higher average output power. The linear relationship between the switching frequency and the average input current is shown in Figure 3. This linear characteristic only exists while the LLC converter operates in DCM and it allows for paralleling multiple LLC converters to support higher power capabilities as discussed above.

Figure 6. Experimental waveforms at $f_s = 46.5$ kHz: voltage across the resonant capacitor, V_{res} , MOSFET's gate voltage, V_{gate} , current on the resonant tank, I_r , current on the secondary of the transformer, I_{sec}

Figure 7. Experimental waveforms at 94.3 kHz: voltage across the resonant capacitor, V_{res} , MOSFET's gate voltage, V_{gate} , current on the resonant tank, I_r , current on the secondary of the transformer, I_{sec}

The waveforms in Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the soft switching that occurs when the switches are turned off. The gate voltage pulse length is a parameter set in the digital controller's software and is based on the resonant period. Through testing, the pulse length is set such that the gate voltage is turned off while the diode is conducting and the voltage across the switches is zero. The effect of ZCS is also observed as each diode stops conducting before the other diode starts conducting. These effects combined result in less

switching losses increasing the efficiency of the LLC converter.

From Figure 6 and Figure 7, the relationship between the primary and secondary current is observed. As expected, using a 1:5.5 turns ratio transformer, the ratio of primary to secondary current results in an observed ratio of 5.43:1 and the waveforms indicate that the transformer is operating in the linear region.

Next, in order to demonstrate that this type of DC-DC converter in DCM of operation is easy to parallel, two LLC converters were assembled in the parallel configuration shown in Figure 8. The circuit parameters are shown in Table I. The PV array consists of two commercial PV modules with a maximum DC output voltage of 21V and output power of 40W. Each LLC converter utilizes a voltage doubler on the output in conjunction with a 1:5.5 ferrite core transformer to boost the output of the PV module to a voltage sufficient enough to charge the storage battery string. Using six 12V lead-acid batteries, the string nominal voltage is 72V. In the lab a DC power supply was used to emulate a battery stack.

Figure 8. Block diagram of the laboratory test set up. The batteries were replaced by a DC power supply set at 75 VDC.

TABLE I. LAB EXPERIMENT PARAMENTERS

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Resonant capacitors	C_r	0.72 μF
Resonant inductor	L_r	2.1 μH
Resonant frequency	f_{res}	128 kHz
PV capacitor	C_{cap}	625 μF
Output capacitor	C_o	30 μF
Input voltage	V_{PV}	18 V
Transformer turns ratio	N_t	1:5.5
Output voltage	V_o	75 V

The P&O MPPT algorithm described in the previous section was implemented in the FPGA controller of the LLC converters. The MPPT sends the switching frequency command f_{sw} to both LLC converters as shown in Figure 8. Its input only needs to be the voltage across the capacitor at

the output of the PV panels V_{cap} . Since a current sensor was available the performance of the MPPT with and without the current sensor input was compared experimentally. Note that the feedback line for the current in Figure 8 is dashed to indicate that it is not always used in the experiments.

Figure 9 displays the experimental waveforms for the system shown in Figure 8, with a DC power supply simulating the battery stack. The gate voltage, resonant voltage, and resonant current are displayed for a single LLC converter while the output current is the combined output from both LLC converters. The output voltage (not displayed) was maintained at 75V using a DC power supply. A resistor bank is connected in parallel with the DC power supply to dissipate the current from both the DC power supply and the LLC converter output. The ripple in the output current I_{out} is a result of both LLC converters using a common gate signal causing the resonant pulses to occur simultaneously. Future development of the PV power conditioning system will include staggered gate signals for multiple LLC converters operated in parallel to interleave the output currents. This will result in reduced ripple in the load current. Note that the current and the resonant frequency shown in Figure 9 are different than the waveforms presented earlier in Figure 6 and Figure 7 because the resonant components were changed to increase the output current.

Figure 9. Experimental waveforms under steady state conditions at approximately 50kHz: voltage across the resonant capacitor V_{res} , MOSFET's gate voltage V_{gate} , resonant current I_r , output current I_{out} .

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the response of the MPPT algorithm with and without current sensor respectively as the power increases. As described in the previous section the feedback from the current sensor at the input of the LLC converters is expendable because it can be replaced by an observer. This is one of the advantages of operating the LLC converter in DCM. The measurements in Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the switching frequency, the LLC converters output power, PV voltage and current while slowly rotating the PV arrays towards the sun over a 20 second period. Figure 12 and Figure 13 also display measurements obtained with and without the current sensor feedback respectively.

These plots show the step response obtained by rotating the PV arrays away from the sun over a 5 second period. This results in a step change in output power. The LLC converter data was recorded using a digital oscilloscope. Because the sampling frequency is reduced in the MPPT algorithm utilizing a current observer, the response to changing environmental conditions is slightly slower than the response of the MPPT algorithm utilizing direct current measurement. Otherwise, the response of the two MPPT algorithms is nearly identical. These figures show that both MPPT algorithms track the optimal operating point while environmental conditions vary both slowly and quickly. Therefore the current sensor is expendable.

Figure 10. LLC converter waveforms when slowly increasing the PV array irradiance using the MPPT algorithm with current sensor.

Figure 11. LLC converter waveforms when slowly increasing the PV array irradiance using the MPPT algorithm w/o current sensor.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The observations made in this paper indicate that the LLC converter in DCM of operation is an attractive DC-DC converter topology to interface a PV module to a DC bus. An LLC converter in DCM behaves very much like a current source, which makes parallel operation simple. This is an

attractive feature when multiple micro-converters interfacing individual PV panels are used instead of centralized inverters interfacing large PV arrays.

The embedded P&O MPPT algorithm ensures that the PV array is operating at its optimum power point, which seeks to improve the efficiency of the PV array. This paper demonstrates that the P&O MPPT algorithm works without a current sensor because the LLC converter in DCM of operation features a linear relationship between the converter input current and switching frequency. Since the PV current can be approximated by the converter average input current, the switching frequency can be used to create a current observer to replace the current sensor.

Figure 12. LLC converter waveforms based on a step decrease of the PV array irradiance using the MPPT algorithm with current sensor.

Figure 13. LLC converter waveforms based on a step decrease of the PV array irradiance using the MPPT algorithm w/o current sensor.

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